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In concert practice, accompanists regularly encounter opera arias, scenes and instrumental concertos in which the piano part is a transcription of the orchestral score. This explains its specific nature: a certain overload of texture, the presence of awkward passages for the performer, and the need to reproduce an "orchestral" sound.

The imperfections of the piano texture of opera and instrumental concerto scores create a number of problems that accompanists and teachers of the "Accompanist Class" constantly encounter in their work, both in their personal practice and in their classes with students. The challenges of concert performance of the piano part in opera arias, scenes and instrumental concertos differ from those of performing the accompaniment in romances, songs and chamber instrumental pieces, where this part was created specifically for the piano. Such accompaniment, created with the instrument's specific characteristics in mind, offers a comfortable texture, the register richness inherent to the grand piano, clear pedaling requirements, and so on.

In contrast, the piano part of a clavier, although intended for piano, is a transcription of music composed for orchestral performance (i.e., an adaptation of the orchestra's large-scale, colorful sound to the capabilities of a single instrument—the piano).

Composers did not always arrange their orchestral works for piano themselves, entrusting this work to other musicians (theoreticians). They, in turn, often failed to consider the technical capabilities and convenience of accompanists in their work, overloading the texture with significant complexities that hinder natural performance, maintaining the required tempos, and the character of the music.

Accompanists are forced to simplify such textures, making them convenient but

sacrificing certain elements of the music. They must seek a more rational method of presentation that promotes clarity and ease of expression.

When performing at a concert, the accompanist must create a full-fledged sonority of the accompaniment, reminiscent of an orchestra with its polyphony and variety of timbres. To achieve this, it is necessary to have a practically playable piano texture. Sometimes, a simple change in fingering and a rearrangement of the hands creates a completely different sonority, evoking the idea of orchestral timbres of the orchestral instruments. The accompanist must approach the presentation of the piano scores critically, simplifying the texture based on the composer's creative goals (for example, the piano scores of P. Tchaikovsky's operas are rich in dense polyphonic texture, while the piano scores of G. Rossini and V. Mozart are distinguished by a transparent orchestration style).

The numerous possible arrangements can be summarized under two main principles:

- minor changes with a different distribution of texture between the hands;
- significant changes in the piano score's texture, resulting in a completely new presentation of complex passages.

Particular attention should be paid to the mechanical transfer of line markings from the score to the piano score (it should be understood that these line markings are intended for performers on orchestral instruments, not pianists).

Another very common error is a mismatch between the dynamic nuances presented in the score and their mechanical transfer to the piano score. An accompanist, when literally interpreting dynamic instructions, cannot know how closely they correspond to the composer's intentions (the F of the trumpet and the F of the viola are completely different, just as the P of the trombone and the P of the oboe).

Thus, understanding orchestral sonority, the dynamics of various instrument groups, the ability to make the piano sound "orchestral," and bringing the texture of the piano score closer to one's own pianistic capabilities—these are the tasks that

accompanists face when working on the piano scores of operas and instrumental concertos.

When working on the piano scores of operas and instrumental works written for orchestra, accompanists face a number of problems: the question of piano introductions and conclusions in separate performances of opera arias, the clarification of dynamic nuances; the creation of an "orchestral" sound while conveying the specific characteristics of various instrument groups; the specifics of articulation and pedal points; the need to alter the texture to facilitate the performance of various keyboard difficulties while preserving the composer's original sound and intent. Solving these numerous problems requires developing automatic skills and abilities, which have been honed in practice by many master accompanists.